

Exploring flows of international students into the UK over the period of 2009-2019 using UCAS Application Data

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Summary

The UK is one of the key destinations for internationally mobile students in the world. It is important to understand the make-up of these ‘flows’ of students into the UK, and data from UCAS can provide new insights into these flows by allowing for the exploration of both the volume of applications and acceptances for different UK institutions for students from a variety of countries. By examining the key ‘flows’ over time, this study attempts to understand the key and emerging markets for internationally mobile students within a context of changing internationalisation policies both within universities and at the level of the UK Government.

Keywords: International student mobility, internationalisation of higher education, flows, network analysis, UCAS, early-career.

1. Definitions

1.1. Internationally Mobile Student

In 2015 UNESCO defined an internationally mobile student in the following way:

“An internationally mobile student is an individual who has physically crossed an international border between two countries with the objective to participate in educational activities in a destination country, where the destination country is different from [their] country of origin.” (UNESCO, 2015)

This definition of an internationally mobile students helps to distinguish individuals whose purpose for moving is solely to study. This type of movement may be more likely to be defined as ‘spatial mobility’ as opposed to migration, due to its temporal nature and allowance for uncertainty in status and tenure (Plane & Rogerson, 2008; King & Raghuram, 2013). However, this is an area of debate due to the potential of individuals to remain in the country after studying (King & Raghuram, 2013).

1.2. Internationalisation

Most research in this area exists within the context of internationalisation of higher education, which can be defined as:

“the process of integrating an international, intercultural, and global dimension into the purpose, functions (teachings, research, and service), and delivery of higher education at institutional and national levels” (Knight, 2008, p.xi)

Internationalisation is a key strategy undertaken by both governments and specific institutions, referring specifically to the key policies and practises undertaken by academic systems in order to manoeuvre a globalised academic environment (Albach & Knight, 2007, p.290).

2. Research Context

The UK is the second largest destination for internationally mobile students in the world, attracting 435,000 international students in 2017 (UNESCO, 2021). The numbers of internationally mobile students attending UK institutions has grown over the past decade, alongside a general growth in the number of internationally mobile students across the globe (HESA, 2021; UNESCO, 2021). Given this large and seemingly continuous growth, it is of interest to both academia and industry what constitutes this growth and where the key markets of demand are.

Much literature on international student mobility (ISM) uses a demand and supply framework to understand the decision-making process of internationally mobile students (Wilkins, et al., 2012). Whilst push-factors are those that force individuals to move from their home country, pull factors attract people to move to a host country (Giddens, et al., 2016; Lee, 1966; Zajda, 2015). In the context of ISM, push factors operate within the home country to initiate the student's decision to study overseas whilst pull factors operate within the host country in order to make that country more attractive (Gonzalez, et al., 2011). Mazzarol and Soutar (2002) describe how it is push factors that make the potential student decide whether they will study internationally, and then pull factors which take precedent when considering where they want to go. This research endeavours to consider the 'pull' factors of the UK when examining the flows of internationally mobile students into the UK.

Growth in the numbers of internationally mobile students exist within a context of internationalisation of higher education, including the purposeful integration of policies which are designed to attract international students by both governments and institutions throughout the years (pull factors). Most UK institutions have publicly available internationalisation strategies, a feature that has become more prominent in recent years (Knight & de Wit, 2018). Many internationalisation strategies focus on growing the institution's reputation abroad as well as building relationships with specific countries and regions. In regards to the national level, prior research has identified three key periods of marketisation of international higher education beginning in 1999 (Lomer, 2018). Whilst the beginning of millennium saw the introduction of strict targets for international students and welcoming immigration policies under the New Labour government, the 2010s saw a maintenance of some targets for international students but a harsher policy environment for immigration. Both contexts see lip-service given to welcoming further international students, but actual policies have not always meshed well with this narrative. The current Conservative government has set up five key actions for international students by relaxing visa requirements and extending the period of post-study leave in addition to policies aimed at marketing and building connections to specific 'high-value' markets (Department for International Trade & Department for Education, 2021). The current goal is to increase the value of 'education exports' to £35bn by 2030, a 4 per cent growth in demand per year (Ibid.) These policy environments depict a variety of contexts for 'pull' into the UK and any changes in flows should be considered alongside these.

The final context worth noting are Brexit and COVID-19. These both pose challenges for the temporal analysis of international student flows. Key changes as a result of Brexit for international students occurred in the 2020/2021 academic year, where EU students changed from home fees to international fees. COVID-19's impact is most likely similarly seen in the 2020/21 and 2021/22 academic years. Due to the anomalous nature of these years, it has been decided to dedicate a separate research project to these years in order to compare to the changes seen in the previous years as will be examined by this study.

3. Research Questions:

- i) What are the key and emerging markets for UK Higher Education to the UK?
- ii) What are they key destination institutions for internationally mobile students?
- iii) How do these markets change alongside ‘pull’ factors within the UK and specific institutions?

4. Data

The data used are provided by the University and Colleges Admission Service (UCAS) who are the partner for this project. UCAS act as the main route of applications for students wanting to apply to UK Higher Education institutions. The data provided include the numbers of applications and acceptances for UK HE institutions as well as the domicile of these applicants amongst other demographic characteristics. The UCAS data are novel in this field, as most other research of this type uses qualitative methods, open-source data, or data for specific institutions only.

5. Methods

The current plan is to analyse the data using network analysis to understand the flows of internationally mobile students into UK institutions. The first stage of the analysis may be fairly descriptive, pinpointing the overall changes and key players demonstrated by the UCAS data. The network analysis will seek to explore in more detail the relationships between sending countries and institutions in the UK. This involves identifying nodes and edges within the data. Whilst the nodes are identified using unique IDs, the edges contain all the information about the connections in the data. The analysis will use RStudio and the packages network, visNetwork and networkD3.

The following figures demonstrate examples of the preliminary exploratory analysis as an example of what the final paper might include:

Figure 1 Changing numbers of Chinese applicants who applied to UK universities via UCAS between 2009 and 2021*

Figure 2 Top numbers applications by country for the 2015 academic year according to UCAS data

Figure 3 Top UK institutions receiving applications from international students in the 2015 academic year

Figure 4. Sankey diagram to show the top 50 flows of international students from their origin country to different UK institutions (interactive)

Figures 1, 2 and 3 show some of the descriptive analysis of the data, showing the changes in the numbers of internationally mobile students in different ways. Figure 1 depicts the changing numbers of Chinese students over the period of the data, including the two extra academic years of 2020 and 2021. As can be seen, there have been large increases in this over time, with a dip only occurring in 2011. Figure 2 shows the key senders to the UK in the 2015 academic year, with China topping the list followed by Malaysia and Hong Kong. Figure 3 shows which UK institutions received the highest numbers of applications from overseas students in 2015, with The University of Edinburgh topping the chart. Finally, Figure 4 shows a sankey diagram as a result of some early network analysis showing the flows between countries and specific universities for a select number of applications. Overall, these provide an example of some of the analysis that will be completed as part of this project. By examining the data in these ways, it is possible to highlight some of the key markets of international students, and also begin examining how these have changed over time.

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Biographies

Currently studying in the second year of an integrated masters and PhD at the Geographic Data Science Lab at the University of Liverpool with UCAS acting as the project partner. Key research interests are international student mobility, internationalisation of higher education and government policy towards international students.